

ESCAPE Collaboration Distributed Computing Roadmap

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(for the ESCAPE Data Infrastructure for Open Science Work Package)

Abstract: This technical note addresses key aspects of distributed computing within the ESCAPE collaboration Research Infrastructures. It outlines a strategic roadmap derived from priorities identified by the experiment's experts to address both current and future challenges. The document is structured around three core pillars: Data Management, Analysis and Workload Management and AAI/Cybersecurity. Each section begins with an executive summary, followed by a more detailed technical analysis. An Appendix is provided with the consolidation of core initiatives into a set of targeted and actionable projects, forming a coherent program of work to guide future development and coordination across the collaboration.

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Distributed Data Management Roadmap

Executive Summary: Consolidate common guidelines and efforts for a Large Scale Distributed Data Management System designed to meet the evolving needs of ESCAPE Research Infrastructures (ERIs).

The system is intended to scale to the Exabyte level, accommodating the entire data lifecycle, from raw data injection at the experiment source to multi-tiered asynchronous data transfers. The proposed strategy builds upon the ESCAPE prototype Data Lake, fostering collaboration to enhance its capabilities. The system aims to embrace data FAIRness: incorporate global replication rules, access policies (including embargo data), enable long-term Data Preservation, and support full data life-cycles, all while maintaining flexibility for integration with diverse infrastructure providers, including HPC centres and cloud services. Additionally, the document suggests further investigations into the integration of Content Delivery and Latency Hiding services for efficient data access.

Purpose:

Develop a potentially common Large Scale Distributed Data Management System model capable of managing data at the Exabyte scale and leverage metadata for European Research Infrastructures. The system will leverage data recording and production phases from raw data injection to multi-tiered asynchronous data transfers, addressing global

replication rules, access policies, and supporting the full data life-cycle. The system should be able to provide access and/or deliver data to the facilities providing computing to the RIs and heterogeneous providers at large. The system should be able to interface with metadata systems or provide metadata services.

Scope:

- Data Management system (Rucio)
 - Scalability: Designing a system that scales seamlessly to Exabyte-level data, accommodating the diverse data production phases within ERIs.
 - Global Replication Rules: Implement global replication rules to facilitate data distribution across multiple sites, ensuring redundancy and availability while adhering to regional and institutional policies.
 - Access Policies: Incorporate robust access policies, including mechanisms for handling embargoed data, ensuring that data access aligns with ethical considerations and regulatory requirements.
 - Full Data Life-Cycle Support: Design the system to support the full data life-cycle, from raw data ingestion to archival. Including custodial (long term preservation) and ephemeral data, by leveraging potential storage quality of service offering from the sites.
- Collaborative Evolution: Building upon the ESCAPE prototype Data Lake and fostering continued collaboration among research infrastructure, computing sites and potential external providers.
- Asynchronous Third Party Copy File Transfer Service (FTS): Global file transferring machinery connecting the different storage systems. File movement “executor backend” of the data management system. Able to speak transfer protocols required by the infrastructure providers: http/webdav, s3/swift; and opened to include new standards.
- Infrastructure Providers: Ensure the system's flexibility by allowing integration with a variety of infrastructure providers, including collaborating data facilities, HPC centres and cloud services. This adaptability ensures that ERIs can leverage diverse computational resources based on their specific needs.
- Content Delivery and Latency Hiding: Conduct further investigations into the integration of Content Delivery and Latency Hiding services to enhance the efficiency of data access. This involves optimising data transfer and access times, improving the overall user experience for researchers accessing the distributed data via caching services or staging areas (data preplacement) at the sites.
- Metadata and Data Discovery: Improve the ability to perform data “cataloguing” with the objective to provide the required metadata-based level of granularity for data discovery and browse-ability by the users. The development could happen in two ways: extending the system capabilities for metadata fields or by facilitating the integration of external metadata sources (eg. Virtual Observatory). A POSIX-like view of the Rucio file catalog will provide a more familiar view for users from the GW community that are used to discover data in /cvmfs/.
- Multi-messenger, multi-wavelength and Open Data ready infrastructure: To be able to combine data from different experiments (detectors, telescopes, radio-antennas, etc.), the data Management systems should be able to provide extended metadata fields and/or interface to experiment's metadata DataBases. Examples are the current Rucio-IVOA integration.

- Advanced monitoring and performance reporting
- Data streaming capability for low-latency analyses: to be able to stream data with defined latency requirements (of the order of a few seconds) to support data processing for alert generation and similar activities.
- Integration of Content Delivery and Latency Hiding services: data caching infrastructures could maximise the potential of a consolidated storage model, eg. Data Lake by hiding latency and orchestrating data delivery workflows. There are three key aspects for potential use of caching technologies:
 - DAQ buffers. RIs and labs needing raw data injection tools and/or data download. Assess deployment of edge services addressing CDN and latency hiding, allowing to interface storage buffers with the Data Lake approach.
 - Storage-less data processing sites: Promote less demanding storage systems to moderately small sites. Sites that do not have special interest in maintaining and operating a full storage system could opt for stateless storage (caches) or storage-less approach and focus towards providing varied resources (CPU, GPU, Machine Learning, etc.) and analysis platforms.
 - Storage edge services (caches) to blend HPC internal storage and RI data/ Accelerate collaboration with FENIX and EuroHPC Joint Undertaking to ensure new federated models of HPC are in sync with EU Science Clusters strategies. Ability to deploy Content Delivery and Latency Hiding as edge services to exploit opportunistic resources.

Data Access and Analysis Framework for Scientific Computing

Executive Summary: This activity aims to deliver a framework of shared methodologies and best practices for data access and analysis for use within ESCAPE Research Infrastructures (ERIs). We focus on developing a modular, scalable analysis platform that ERIs can build on and customize to meet their individual needs. The platform will integrate data discovery and analysis services — ranging from interactive computational notebooks and visualization tools to bulk data processing systems — with large-scale data management services, such as data lakes and content delivery networks. The platform will support reproducible analyses and long-term preservation of results.

Preamble: This work builds on the VRE and ESAP efforts undertaken in the ESCAPE project. These efforts were complementary, with the VRE providing an integrated environment for accessing known resources (data, CPUs, software and reproducibility engine), while ESAP focused on helping users find data, services, and resources across heterogeneous infrastructures. By combining these efforts, we are able to provide a complete solution covering data access and data processing together with visualization, discovery and browsing at all scales, from individual systems to globally distributed networks.

Purpose: The purpose of this framework is to enhance the capabilities of experiments in data processing for end-users by providing a platform for data access and analysis, leveraging interactive notebooks and integrating advanced data management services. This framework aims to streamline the research process, to minimise the time to get first results, ensure seamless access to data, software, and to foster reproducibility.

Scope

- **Analysis Platform Core:** Common framework as an entry point to deliver modular, extensible, and scalable services designed to meet the diverse needs of research infrastructures. Based on consolidated APIs for data management, batch and interactive processing, and consolidated AAI credentials across platforms. Highly customizable to RI individual requirements, the platform lowers the barrier to entry for new researchers while accelerating their transition from exploratory tests to full-scale analyses.
- **Scalability:** Remove the need to distinguish between interactive tests and full-scale runs by providing users with one coherent analysis platform capable of both, sending work to additional sites if needed. Promote environmentally responsible computing by providing an analysis platform that produces meaningful results for small scale tests. Make transition to full-scale runs transparent for the user, encouraging the use of test runs to avoid wasting resources.
- **Data Access:** Low friction access to data products, both stored on local (possibly shared) filesystems and in remote repositories, using POSIX-like interfaces or abstraction layers where processings can integrate virtualized file systems.
- **Bulk Data Management:** The platform will integrate large-scale data management services, including data lake technologies, and expose the data they provide to interactive analysis systems.
- **Latency Hiding and Fast Data Access:** By leveraging content delivery networks (CDNs) we will be able to optimise data access by hiding latency and access times,

providing a responsive and reliable platform for users. In particular, we will continue to investigate and integrate the XCache service derived from XRootD.

- Content Delivery Networks: By leveraging CDNs we will be able to optimise data access by hiding latency, ensuring fast and reliable data delivery and a seamless interactive user experience.
- Interactive Notebooks: The interactive computational notebook, as provided by e.g. Jupyter, forms the basis of modern collaborative research environments. The platform will provide rich support for these notebooks, enabling researchers to create, share, and reproduce analyses easily, e.g. using the REANA system.
- Bulk Data Processing: The ability to efficiently define and run at-scale processing of bulk data using batch workflows and other cluster processing tools (e.g. Dask or DIRAC). And also to scale up not just to a large number of jobs, but to very large jobs (e.g. Slurm clusters and HPC workload management systems interfaces).
- Sustainable ecosystem: The key components — tools and services — will be developed in an open way, with wide buy-in from the RIs and (where possible) the wider community. In this way, we will build a sustainable and long-lasting software ecosystem.
- Reproducibility and Preservation: Tools and mechanisms to ensure reproducibility of analyses and results, including version control, containerization, and standards for long-term analysis preservation, will be deeply integrated into the system.
- Environmental impact: Implement tools that capture computing resource usage in a standardised way, allowing users to understand their computing and energy footprint so that they can make more sustainable choices.
- Interoperability: Ensure interoperability with existing research infrastructures, platforms, and services. The ESCAPE platform should seamlessly integrate with data repositories, analysis tools, and existing platforms, fostering a connected and interoperable research ecosystem. In particular fostering IVOA standards compliance to smoothen and eliminate cross-science boundaries (e.g. multi-wavelength analysis)
- Security and Privacy: Implement robust security measures to safeguard sensitive research data and analyses. This includes encryption, access controls, and regular security assessments to maintain the integrity and confidentiality of research activities.
- Software Distribution and Discovery : Develop and integrate systems that provide convenient distribution of software applications delivered by both RIs themselves and individual science users or teams. We plan to base this work on existing tools (e.g. CernVMFS, EESSI). Integration with the ESCAPE's OSSR to offer the possibility for Software Discovery integrated in the platform.
- Login and User Access
- Multi-RI support for VRE: As large collaborations will very likely host their own instances of a DataLake, VREs will in general need to be able to access multiple DataLake instances within the same environment to support multi-RI workflows.
- Support for low-latency data processing: to be able to process data streaming with defined latency requirements (of the order of a few seconds) to support alert generation and similar activities.
- Accounting and agreements with resource providers

Milestones

- 2024: Build a community around the common tools to ensure its evolution progress in the right direction. Ensure a return value in the form of contributions from all partners in the maintenance and evolution of the tools (eg. the VRE working group)
- 2024: One XCache service in place in at least one of the VRE platforms accessing Data Lake
- 2025: Interconnection of at least two caching and CDN services across one RI (data request routed via caches, later if no match, Data Lake download)
- 2025: Evaluation about the advantages of distributed storage with posix possibilities to be mounted at local facilities
- 2024: CVMFS (or alike) tested in place. At least two RIs testing, prototyping or evaluating
- 2025: CVMFS (or alike) mounted on at least two VRE/AFs
- 2025: VRE/AF able to provide an encapsulation “button” to freeze the analysis (software, code and data pointers). REANA-like service in place in one of the VREs/AF.
- 2025: Distribute analysis capsule off-the-notebook processing facility (HPCs, clouds, etc.)
- 2025: one VRE with the ability to perform Dask-style off-loading from the VRe and the AF.

Conclusion: The proposed Data Access and Analysis Framework aims to empower European researchers within ERIs by providing a unified model as an analysis platform for data access and analysis. By leveraging interactive notebooks, integrating data lake technologies, and optimising data access through CDNs, this framework supports a collaborative and efficient research environment while addressing the critical aspects of reproducibility and long-term analysis preservation.

European Research Infrastructure Trust Framework: Authentication, Authorization, Identity Management and Cyber-Security

Executive Summary: This document outlines a proposal to establish a common model of identity trust across ESCAPE Research Infrastructures (ERIs). The objective is to ensure seamless and secure access to data management services, analysis facilities, and resources while fostering collaboration and interoperability. The framework aims to enhance the overall cybersecurity posture of ERIs, protect sensitive information, and facilitate cross-institutional research.

Purpose:

The purpose of this framework is to **establish standardised practices** for authentication, authorization, and identity management within the European research community. By implementing a **common layer of trust**, ERIs can promote collaboration, streamline access to resources, and ensure the integrity of shared identities **across diverse platforms**. Continue the alignment and engagement with the work done in ESCAPE with EOSC related to AAI federations; together with service providers, the European Science Clusters and the EOSC.

Scope:

- **Authentication:** Verifying the identity of users and systems accessing ERIs
- **Authorization:** Determining access privileges based on authenticated identities
- **Identity Management:** Maintaining and synchronising user identities across data management services, analysis facilities, and resources
- **Federated Identity:** ERIs should adopt a federated identity model to enable users to access services across different institutions using a single set of credentials. This promotes a seamless user experience and encourages collaboration.
- **attribute-based access control mechanisms** to grant permissions based on specific user attributes, enhancing granularity and flexibility in authorization.
- **Standardised Protocols:** Implement industry-standard protocols such as SAML 2.0, OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect for authentication and authorization processes. This ensures compatibility and interoperability across different systems,
- **Identity Provider (IdP):** Experiments as Identity Providers to authenticate users and manage their identities. This IdP should support single sign-on (SSO) capabilities to enhance user convenience.
- **Attribute Authority:** Implement an Attribute Authority to manage and distribute user attributes required for authorization decisions. This ensures that only authorised users gain access to specific resources. Leverage the current ESCAPE IAM service.
- **Security Measures:** Promote the use of multi-factor authentication to enhance the security of user identities. MFA adds an additional layer of protection, mitigating the risk of unauthorised access.
- **Auditing and Logging:** Implement comprehensive auditing and logging mechanisms to track authentication and authorization events. This facilitates traceability and enables prompt response to security incidents.

- Common Security Hub: Improve early communication, coordinated actions and reactions to cyber-security threads. Strengthen interfaces with already ongoing projects and bodies of Cyber-security, eg. WLCG
- Data Protection: Provide resources to ERIs for best practice on Data Protection. Services that can be accessed via an AAI system will require Data Protection Plans/MoUs/ToS agreements. Compliance with relevant data protection regulations, such as GDPR and HIPAA, on the storage and transmission of user information is required.
- User management

Milestones

- 2024: Roadmap for a common AAI framework: proxies for IdP aggregation and RIs “users database” able to manage their users.
- 2025: clusters able to authenticate on IAM (or via proxy), get tokens and access the DL infrastructure
- 2026: IdM in place, RIs user database able to interact with the global IAM system (ban/renew/update)

Conclusion: The proposed Authentication, Authorization, and Identity Management framework aim to provide ERIs with a common layer of trust, fostering collaboration and ensuring the security of shared identities. Implementation of these principles and components will contribute to a more robust AAI and cybersecurity infrastructures, supporting the European research community in its pursuit of scientific excellence. Activities scoped in alignment with related AAI federation activities in the EOSC and the Science Clusters.

Appendix: Program of Work - Targeted Project Cards

Summary	[DIOS-1]: Cross System Open Data Access
Benefit Hypothesis	Foster data shareability across science domains (eg. multi-wavelength) and efficient usage of storage resources. Potential benefits for all ESFRIS. Immediate impact for CERN, and the HL-LHC experiments ATLAS and CMS.
Description and target outcomes	Ability to share and access Open Data across Rucio instances will facilitate combination of data for Analysis purposes (multi-wavelength) and also save considerable amount of resources at the storage level at the sites (data does not need to be physically duplicated). Potential interests from all ESFRIS, but immediate interest for CERN, and the HL-LHC experiments ATLAS and CMS
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIS]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

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Summary	[DIOS-2]: multi-tenant (multiple virtual organisation) rucio: - what is needed? who is keen? Should the ESCAPE prototype be made multi-vo? (Mieke to follow-up offline, possibility to look at km3net Rucio instance as part of multi-vo)
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIS]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-3]: user (independent) data flows: good to add user data management scripts as new features into Rucio to support user flows, understand what different flows look like (Martin, Mario, Frederic, Rosie to work on)
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIS]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-4]: embargoes / access policies (Rucio) token-based access need to have testing against new embargoed use cases
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	

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Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-5]: Extending/consolidating FTS protocols for HPC: s3/swift testbed
Benefit Hypothesis	Integration of EuroHPC centers in the EOSC as computing endpoints for a diverse range of scientific workloads
Description and target outcomes	Leverage punctual HPC resources with the Data Management system via FTS. Ability to pre-place data from Rucio via FTS in the internal hierarchical storage systems of HPC (via edge services or caching), this allow to schedule and run predefined workloads at the HPCs.
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-6]: Data acquisition - MAGIC / CTAO buffer? outstanding work?
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	Develop a proposed template for data acquisition into Rucio from remote data generation sites
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-7]: Edge services - HPC staging area? build RSE on top of existing storage to allow rucio to copy data directly into HPCs.
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-8]: How can we support low-latency (urgent) data replication for e.g. Gravitational Wave / Target of opportunity cases?
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]

Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS]: Metadata query scalability with Rucio
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	<p>While the current design of the bulk data management system of CTAO puts the metadata management outside of Rucio, one possible contribution could be to investigate the interface between bulk data management and workload to support metadata-based queries. The methods "setMetadata" and "getMetadata" have already been developed and successfully used by the "Belle II" experiment. This contribution aims to implement the "query" method. Additionally, a high emphasis on performance requirements for these metadata methods and requires precise benchmarking. Two key parameters may significantly impact performance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The complexity of metadata queries (including the number and types of parameters). 2. The backend used to store metadata (NoSQL DB, Relational DB).
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-9]: does the data management system publish data to the Virtual Organisation via the data registry, i.e. is this an interface to be worked on?
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	<p>[DIOS-10]: Hierarchical resources management capabilities in Rucio</p> <p>The project aims at evolving the RUCIO system in order to allow a hierarchical federation of multiple instances. The main motivations are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . To simplify the operations of a possibly complex system . To enable a highly dynamic model where storage backends (RSE) can come and go on demand (i.e. accommodating integration of systems like word class HPC machines).
Benefit Hypothesis	The vRSE will introduce an increase in flexibility over the topology supported for a data-lake, enabling, among other solutions, the creation and prototyping of a PoC based on a federation of RUCIO instances.
Description and target outcomes	<p>Responsibility delegation and hiding of finer granularity.</p> <p>The RSE resources are the RUCIO representation of a storage entity capable of storing and serving data via well defined interfaces, mostly for Third Party Copy (TPC) and upload/download phases of a file. Our proposal is to create a particular RSE type that can abstract the physical interactions of a real file system to a more generic interface where the final destination/source of a file transfer/movement can be anything</p>

	<p>including another independent RUCIO instance with a set of physical RSE that are not known by the RUCIO parent instance. We will refer to this abstraction as “virtual RSE” (vRSE).</p> <p>The proposed model foresees vRSE interacting with the RUCIO components just like a normal RSE does. Any relevant new component will be managed via a plugin based approach aiming to make everything flexible to accommodate further extensions to other case studies. We foresee two interfaces: The PFN2LFN algorithm will return custom and possibly dynamic/temporary results, asking the plugin implementation for making then translation</p> <p>In the case of a nested RUCIO instance, the plugin will ask the “child” RUCIO instance for a PFN</p> <p>The physical endpoint of the storage can change dynamically; the creation of an inbound and outbound FTS transfer should not rely on a fixed storage endpoint name.</p> <p>For nested RUCIO instances, the FTS src or destination endpoint will depend on where the data are physically stored.</p> <p>The internals of the core RUCIO components are built around the concept of a unique physical storage behind an RSE. Thus we do expect to take care of any place where this implication will not allow a dynamic generation of Physical File Names (PFN) and FTS transfers.</p> <p>Moreover the overall requirement is that FTS should be able to trigger transfers from the underlying vRSE endpoint, all the storage should then allow the parent RUCIO proxy to write and read.</p>
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	A few PMs from each of the proponents. One contract @ CERN + One contract @ INFN (ideally 24 months each)
Skills needed	Experience in the development and deployment of RUCIO. Experience in distributed (storage) infrastructures

Summary	[DIOS-11]: Lifecycle data management: archived data vs ephemeral
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	<p>CTAO uses Rucio at the base of its bulk data management system and DIRAC for the workload management for its batch processing. To design CTAO's data processing workflow effectively, the integration of Rucio with DIRAC is crucial. The data processing workflows are designed to leverage metadata conditions for accessing the appropriate input files. Thus, it becomes important where the catalogue of metadata is managed (inside the data management system or in the workload management system). This setup will largely benefit from the interface of the data management and workload systems and improvements to replication rules (i.e. supporting long, medium, and short-term storage (caching, staging)), access policies, FTS tuning, and scalability. One of our main identified problems right now is how to implement the separation of long-term archived data from ephemeral (short-term) data produced during data processing. Our current expectation is to use Rucio for both of these, but with very different policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term: no replication, data routed to specific storage elements close to local data processing, optional policy to remove/clean data automatically after a set period of time • Long-term: full replication policy, no data removal allowed
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]

Summary	[DIOS-12]: Rucio FUSE-posix interface to make Rucio namespace POSIX-mountable
Benefit Hypothesis	
Description and target outcomes	In the Gravitational Wave community (LIGO, VIRGO) data are traditionally distributed on cvmfs, therefore scientists are used to discover data using a POSIX-like interface. The idea is to expose the Rucio file

	<p>catalog according to a structure like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the root of the mount is intended to be a cvmfs-like "/rucio"; • the first level of the tree (namely /rucio/*) should be filled with all the available scopes; • each scope should appear as a directory filled with its DiDs; • file DiDs will appear as files; • container and dataset DiDs will appear as directories;
Priority value	[weighted sum of priority from ESCAPE ESFRIs]
Sizing estimate	[how many person months]
Skills needed	[what competencies does someone need to have to undertake this work]